

Supplementary

Emergent ferromagnetism and interface exchange bias in self-assembled copper-fullerene hybrid nanostructures

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Figure S1. Experimental (dots) and theoretical (red lines) Raman spectra of the SA Cu_xC_{60} hybrid films with Cu concentrations of $x=3.6$ (a) and $x=8.5$ (b). The broad peak detected nearly pentagonal pinch mode of C_{60} , $A_g(2)$, has been deconvoluted using three Lorentzians filled by different colors. Brown Lorentzian centered at 1469 cm^{-1} corresponds to pristine C_{60} molecules; pink and blue filled Lorentzians centered respectively at 1464 cm^{-1} and 1459 cm^{-1} correspond to the coupled C_{60} molecules (see main text).

Analysis of the complex Raman peak around the C_{60} $A_g(2)$ vibrational mode shows that the normalized intensity of the shifted modes, which correspond to the coupled C_{60} molecules (at 1464 cm^{-1} and at 1459 cm^{-1} , I_1 and I_2) is clearly larger in HC sample ($x=8.5$) than that of the respective modes in the LC sample ($x=3.6$). The mentioned mode intensities were normalized by the mode intensity of the pristine (nonmagnetic) C_{60} molecules (at 1469 cm^{-1} , I_0). In particular, for the deconvoluted modes in the spectra of the LC and HC samples we respectively have: $I_1/I_0 = 0.34$, $I_2/I_0 = 0.61$ (for LC) and $I_1/I_0 = 0.76$, $I_2/I_0 = 0.88$ (for HC). So, the increase of the normalized intensity of the shifted modes (corresponding to the coupled C_{60} molecules) in the HC sample in respect to the LC sample can be found as: $0.76/0.34 = 2.23$ (for the mode at 1464 cm^{-1}) and $0.88/0.61 = 1.44$ (for the mode at 1459 cm^{-1}). The calculated results show the relative increase of number of the coupled C_{60} molecules caused by increase of x from 3.6 to 8.5 in the SA films. Evidently, such a change in the SA film nanostructure can influence the saturation magnetization of the film.